

1 **COMT activation in Alzheimer's Disease.**

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6 We pioneered whole transcriptome analysis of gene expression changes associated with the
7 neurodegenerative disease ALS: in induced pluripotent stem cells and human tissues, in the motor
8 neurons and in patient fibroblasts (1). Studying a second, rare neurodegenerative disease featuring
9 expression of TDP-43, Tau and alpha synuclein revealed activation of a molecule functioning in dopamine
10 metabolism known as COMT (2). We then measured and described COMT activation to an extent
11 greater than virtually all genes in the transcriptome in ALS (1), and in patients with Parkinson's Disease (3,
12 4).

13 We present evidence here demonstrating that activation of COMT can be observed in induced pluripotent
14 stem cells of humans with Alzheimer's Disease. COMT induction occurs concomitant with amyloid
15 expression. Thus, we have now described COMT expression as a signature transcriptional feature of
16 three separate neurodegenerative diseases: ALS, PD, and AD.
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Results

We measured total transcription in two induced pluripotent stem cell culture systems *in vitro* to address difficulties in studying Alzheimer's Disease biology late in disease *in vivo*: a culture system in which cortical neurons cultured for 80 days were derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered by CRISPR to contain a mutation in PSEN1 found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease, and a second induced pluripotent stem cell (hiPS) culture system in which neurons were derived from hiPS engineered to contain a variant of amyloid precursor protein gene APP known as the Swedish mutation (K595N/M596L), comparing total transcription to isogenic iPS containing wild-type APP.

Induction of COMT in cortical neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells.

GSE128343

Figure 1: COMT is produced in induced pluripotent stem cells containing the PSEN1 M164V mutation found in patients with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease.

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1312	4.88E-02	0.1307	-1.9702096	-0.25741304	182.91	COMT	8744/19352	54.8

Engineered PSEN1 M164V mutation resulted in induction of COMT in cortical neurons derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells (hiPS) in culture (Figure 1), demonstrating that a mutation found in patients with early-onset Alzheimer's Disease was sufficient to result in biologically relevant levels of COMT. We recently discovered induction of COMT in iPS cultures from humans with Parkinson's Disease and humans with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, albeit at higher levels.

We next examined a second culture system in which neurons derived from hiPS were engineered to contain a variant in the APP gene, Swe/Swe, comparing total transcription by RNA-sequencing to an isogenic hiPS line containing wild-type APP. Like we found in cells derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells containing PSEN1 M164V (accompanying manuscript) we found that engineered Swedish mutation (APP K595N/M596L) was sufficient to activate both amyloid beta production and COMT (Figure 2).

Expression of high levels of COMT and APP in neurons derived from induced pluripotent stem cells engineered to express the Swedish mutation, a variant of APP found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease.

Figure 2: Both COMT and APP are transcriptionally activated in induced pluripotent stem cells containing the Alzheimer's Disease Swedish mutation Swe/Swe.

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GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
1312	5.35e-03	0.1481	-2.7849696	-0.41248277	191.78	COMT	7603/19645	61.3
351	2.15e-17	0.068	-8.4851528	-0.57691186	15148.03	APP	1186/19645	94.0

Finally, we examined total transcription in the brains (posterior cingulate cortex) of humans with Alzheimer's Disease; these patients were between the age of 40 and 60, and contained *PSEN1* mutations M139T, V89L, or E120G.

1 **Figure 3: COMT is present at high levels in the brains of humans with Alzheimer's Disease**
2 **containing mutations in PSEN1.**

3 GSE39420

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GeneID	p-value	t	B	log2FoldChange	Gene	Rank	%DE
807128	1.19e-03	-4.04	-0.760623	-5.87e-01	COMT	1564/33297	95.3

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6 High levels of COMT were expressed in the posterior cingulate in humans with AD (Figure 3).

7 **Discussion**

8 We presented here evidence that two separate mutations found in humans with Alzheimer's
9 Disease are sufficient to result in high-level expression of a gene (*COMT*) whose expressed product forms
10 functions in dopamine metabolism and is similarly found, differentially expressed transcriptionally induced
11 at levels surpassing the majority of the neuronal transcriptome in human induced pluripotent stem cell
12 models of amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and Parkinson's Disease. The data suggest that COMT is a major
13 contributing factor to neurodegeneration in three major human neurodegenerative diseases: AD, PD, and
14 ALS.
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Methods

We used RNA-sequencing (GSE128343) to measure total transcription in neuronal cell types derived from human induced pluripotent stem cells that had been engineered to contain mutations found in patients with Alzheimer's Disease. We used a second dataset (GSE39420) measuring total transcription in whole brain tissue of Alzheimer's Disease patients containing mutations in PSEN1.